

Metaheuristic-based Adaptive Hybrid Algorithm for solving Constrained Optimization Problems

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ABSTRACT

In this paper a novel Adaptive Hybrid Optimization technique based on Evolutionary and Swarm Intelligence Meta-heuristic methods is formulated and tested in solving complex optimization problems. The hybrid utilizes some of the mostly studied and applied metaheuristic methods in the hybridization and adaptation process with the aim of suppressing their individual weaknesses while taking advantages of the associated individual strengths. The proposed approach combines the strengths of Differential Evolution (DE) and Bacterial Foraging Optimization Algorithms (BFOA) in the hybridization while their weaknesses are mitigated by the introduction of important Genetic Algorithm (GA) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) characteristics in the algorithm formulation. The developed algorithm is tested on the high dimensional Standard Benchmark Functions (F1-F10) as well as two constrained engineering optimization problems (Pressure vessel design and tension/compression spring design). The obtained results are compared with those obtained by other researchers using other well-known metaheuristic optimization methods. When subjected to solving the standard benchmark functions the developed algorithm outperformed the rest of the optimization methods in eight out of the ten test functions. In addition, the developed algorithm produced superior results for the two constrained engineering optimization problems when compared to other meta-heuristic methods.

Key words: Meta-heuristic methods, BFOA, GA, PSO, DE

INTRODUCTION

Different methods and techniques have been formulated to solve various optimization problems. These methods can broadly be classified into for main groups namely: deterministic (mathematic/exact) methods, heuristic (approximate) methods, metaheuristic methods and hybrid methods. Deterministic methods include the unconstrained methods which convert constrained problems into unconstrained form. These methods include all mathematical models which are focused on optimization processes with objective function minimization/maximization subject to sets of constraints [1]. They mainly include the classical programming approaches (e.g. Linear Programming (LP), Dynamic Programming (DP), Quadratic Programming, Non-Linear Programming (NLP) etc.) and decomposition techniques (e.g. Benders Decomposition (BD), Hierarchical Decomposition (HD), Branch & Bound Algorithm (BBA) among others). When solving complex optimization problems which are often nonlinear and non-convex, the computational effort in these deterministic methods is usually huge. In such scenarios, many of these methods require the relaxation of the binary to continuous variables to lower computation burden, however this may lead to solutions far from the optimum [2]. In addition, due to intrinsic limitations of the searching process there is a possibility that the obtained optimal solution corresponds to a local optimum.

Heuristic methods are inventive techniques based on users' experience and hence their computational performance is usually better than that of the mathematical methods. They can be interactive or non-interactive. Interactive heuristic methods interact with the planner in their step-by-step generation, evaluation, and selection of expansion options, while non-interactive do not [2]. Most combinatorial problems cannot be solved to optimality in reasonable computation times, due to their dimensionality or other characteristics. Being exact in most practical optimization problems may be meaningless, since one is dealing with not very precise data in addition to simple simplifications of reality. However, the integrity of the input data, technique used and the solution should be within the acceptable limits. Though heuristic methods can give good feasible solutions with reasonable computation efforts, they are however problem-dependent

and require parameter tuning. Thus, they do not guarantee global solution attainment. Such methods include: Sensitivity Analysis, Depth First Search (DeFS), Best First Search (BeFS), Scenario Analysis etc.

Metaheuristic methods combine the attributes of both deterministic and approximate methods. Unlike heuristic methods, they are not problem-dependent however some intrinsic parameter fine tuning is necessary in their adaptation to specific problems. In these approaches, the constraints and objective functions in the problem formulation are not differentiated since the approaches need no prior knowledge of the problem. The fact that these methods are not gradient-based (derivative-free) helps them avoid premature convergence as a result of being trapped in local optima. Their independence from the starting point (initial solution) eliminates the necessity for convexity in solving optimization problems. Available metaheuristic methods can be classified into three groups namely: Evolutionary Algorithm (EA) approaches (e.g. Evolutionary Programming (EP), Genetic Algorithm (GA), Evolution Strategies (ES), Differential Evolution (DE), Artificial Immune Systems (AIS) etc.); Swarm Intelligence Approaches (e.g. Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Ant Colony Optimization (ACO), Bat Algorithm (BA), Bee Colony Optimization (BCO), Artificial Bee Colony (ABC), Bacterial Foraging Optimization Algorithm (BFOA) etc.) and Trajectory Metaheuristic Approaches (e.g. Hill Climbing (HC), Simulated Annealing (SA), Tabu Search (TS), Greedy Randomized Adaptive Search Procedures (GRASP), Teacher Learning Algorithm (TLA), Biogeography-Based Optimization (BBO) etc.

In the recent past, researchers in this area are hybridizing various techniques to come up with powerful but less complex methods which can be used to solve the different optimization problems. These hybrids techniques are formed by combining two or more of the above reviewed techniques. Hybrids can be between/among methods in the same category or in different categories [2]. In most cases these researchers combine a deterministic approach with a heuristic or meta-heuristic approach. Recently, there is increasing hybridization of heuristic and meta-heuristic methods. The reason for this increased use of hybrids is because they exalt the strengths and improve the weaknesses of the methods concerned. This paper presents a novel metaheuristic-based adaptive hybrid approach developed by combining the attributes of evolutionary techniques with those of swarm intelligence techniques. Table-1 gives the attribute(s) of interest for each optimization technique used in the hybridization process and the reason behind its selection.

Table -1 Details on selection of Optimization Techniques

Optimization Technique	Attribute of Interest	Reason for Selection
DE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Real-valued continuous space application Differential recombination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ease of application to a wide variety of real valued problems with multi-modal, multi-dimensional spaces [3]. Gives better results in comparison to other EA in most cases [4].
BFOA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Easily adaptable Relatively new with increasing application Powerful among swarm intelligence techniques 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Its formulation accommodates best attributes from other techniques easily (ease of improvement) [5]. Often outperforms other swarm intelligence techniques [6].
GA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cross over Mutation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> These properties of the GA bring diversity to the candidate solutions thus discouraging premature convergence [7]. Can provide a good guidance for PSO particles thus improving its efficiency [8].
PSO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global best Individual best 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This attribute can be used to bring the useful social/historical information of particle positions leading to faster convergence [9].

Evolutionary techniques are based on the powerful principle of evolution, that is, survival of the fittest. They explore biological evolution mechanisms such as reproduction, mutation, recombination (crossover) and selection [10-12]. On the other hand, Swarm Intelligence (SI) approaches exhibit the swarm intelligence phenomenon where the collective behavior of agents interacting locally within their environment in a system causes coherent functional global patterns to emerge [2]. The evolutionary techniques utilized in this hybridization are Genetic Algorithm and Differential Evolution while the swarm intelligence techniques are Particle Swarm Optimization and Bacterial Foraging Optimization Algorithm. The hybridization and adaptation process aims at maximizing on individual benefits while avoiding the associated weaknesses. Detailed steps in the formulation of each variant/type of the four metaheuristic techniques used in this hybridization are given in [5-8].

PROPOSED ALGORITHM FORMULATION

As mentioned in the introduction, the metaheuristic-based adaptive hybrid algorithm proposed in this paper combines both genetic and swarm intelligence characteristics. The developed algorithm is majorly based on a hybrid of Differential Evolution (DE) and Bacterial Foraging Optimization Algorithms (BFOA), however, various steps in the developed hybrid are adapted through selected Genetically Improved Particle Swarm Optimization (GIPSO) attributes

so as to be able to mitigate some of the foreseeable weakness in the optimization process. The algorithm is thus abbreviated ADEBFOA (Adaptive Differential Evolution - Bacteria Foraging hybrid optimization algorithm).

Proposed Hybridization and Adaptation Steps

1. The algorithm starts by initializing all the parameters of the techniques involved. These include:
 - Population size (number of bacteria/particles), N
 - Chemotactic steps, N_c
 - Swim length, N_s
 - Reproduction steps, K
 - Elimination/Dispersal steps, L
 - Step-size limits, C_{min} & C_{max}
 - Mutation probability, P_{mut}
2. The N population is randomly initialized taking into account all relevant constraints for which the already formulated objective function is being optimized (minimized/maximized) subject to.
3. The fitness of each bacterium/particle is evaluated based on the optimization problem objective function. The value of each bacterium P , becomes its personal best denoted, P_{best} . The bacterium with the best fitness in this step is denoted as global best denoted, G_{best} .

$$P_{best}^i = P^i, \quad \forall i \quad (1)$$

$$G_{best} = P_{best}^i \text{ if } f(P_{best}^i) = \min\{f(P^i)\}, \quad i \in N \quad (2)$$

4. The iterations are initialized in this stage starting with Elimination/dispersal loop;

$$l = 1, \quad l \in L \quad (3)$$

5. Start reproduction loop;

$$k = 1, \quad k \in K \quad (4)$$

6. Start chemotaxis loop;

$$j = 1, \quad k \in N_c \quad (5)$$

(i) Unlike in normal BFOA, the chemotactic step here is performed employing an adapted step-size based on GIPSO attributes:

(ii) The chemotactic movement for a classical BFOA is represented in (6) and (7).

$$P_{(j+1,k,l)}^i = P_{j,k,l}^i + C(i)\phi(i) \quad (6)$$

$$P_{(j+1,k,l)}^i = P_{j,k,l}^i + C(i) \frac{\Delta(i)}{\sqrt{\Delta^T(i)\Delta(i)}} \quad (7)$$

Where: $P_{j,k,l}^i$ is the position of the i^{th} bacterium in population N at the j^{th} chemotactic step in N_c steps, k^{th} reproduction step in K steps and l^{th} elimination in L elimination steps, $C(i)$ is the step size in the random direction and $\phi(i)$ is a unit vector in the random direction.

(iii) In a classical PSO algorithm, the velocity and position is updated based on equations (8) and (9) respectively.

$$V_{j+1}^i = wV_j^i + c_1r(P_{best_i} - S_j^i) + c_2r(G_{best} - S_j^i) \quad (8)$$

$$S_{j+1}^i = S_j^i + V_{j+1}^i \quad (9)$$

Where: V_j^i and S_j^i are the velocity and position of the i^{th} particle in the population, c_1 and c_2 are weight coefficients for each term respectively and r is a random integer between 0 and 1.

(iv) These classical PSO equations can be used to improve the chemotactic movement for a classical BFOA by incorporating social behavior between the bacteria. In this case, the new BFOA movement is represented as in (10);

$$P_{(j+1,k,l)}^i = P_{j,k,l}^i + C(i)\{(P_{best_i} - P_{j,k,l}^i) + (G_{best} - P_{j,k,l}^i)\} \quad (10)$$

(v) This social cooperation ensures both exploration and exploitation in the search process. As a result, it enhances the probability of searching/moving towards better areas as good information is fully utilized.

(vi) However, premature convergence may arise when P_{best} and G_{best} are located in the same local optimum. In addition, if P_{best} and G_{best} are located on opposite sides of $P_{j,k,l}^i$ oscillations will result. To avoid these limitations the social cooperation analysis is modified using the attributes of Evolutionary Algorithms, i.e. cross-over and mutation. Arithmetic crossover commonly used in Differential Evolution is performed between the P_{best} of each bacterium and the G_{best} to generate a off-spring P_{ideal_i} which is mutated using a mutation probability, P_{mut} as shown in (11) and (12) respectively:

$$P_{ideal}^i = \begin{cases} \alpha P_{best_i} + (1 - \alpha)G_{best}, & \text{if } f(P_{best_i}) < f(P_{r,d}) \\ P_{r,d} & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

$$P_{ideal}^i = \begin{cases} P_{ideal}^i + r\Delta P_{ideal}^i, & \text{if } r < P_m \\ P_{ideal}^i & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

(vii) Using the P_{ideal}^i obtained in (12) the chemotactic movement given in (10) becomes:

$$P_{(j+1,k,l)}^i = P_{j,k,l}^i + C(i)\{(P_{ideal}^i - P_{j,k,l}^i)\} \quad (13)$$

(viii) To balance between the exploration (diversification) and exploitation (intensification) ability of the DE-ABFOA algorithm, the step size is varied to enhance exploration at earlier stages of chemo-taxis and exploitation at later stages.

$$C_{j,k,l}^i = C_{max} - \frac{(C_{max} - C_{min})}{N_c} \cdot j \tag{14}$$

Equation (14) ensures larger step size at initial stages to guarantee the exploration ability while as the iteration move towards the stopping criterion smaller step sizes are adopted to intensify search around the promising areas and thus enhance algorithm's convergence.

(ix) The P_{best} and G_{best} for each bacterium and the population respectively are then updated using (15) and (16).

$$P_{best(j+1,k,l)}^i = \begin{cases} P_{(j+1,k,l)}^i & \text{if } f(P_{(j+1,k,l)}^i) < f(P_{best(j,k,l)}^i) \\ P_{best(j,k,l)}^i & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{15}$$

$$G_{best(j+1)}^i = \begin{cases} P_{best(j+1)}^i & \text{if } f(P_{best(j+1)}^i) < f(G_{best(j)}^i) \\ G_{best(j)}^i & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{16}$$

(x) Start Swim loop inside the chemotactic step for N_s swims,

$$s = 1, \quad s \leq N_s \tag{17}$$

- a) Update the position of the bacteria using (13).
- b) Evaluate the fitness of the new bacteria population.
- c) Update bacterium's P_{best} and G_{best} using (18) & (19).

$$P_{best(s+1)}^i = \begin{cases} P_{(s+1)}^i & \text{if } f(\theta_{(s+1)}^i) < f(P_{best(s)}^i) \\ P_{best(s)}^i & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{18}$$

$$G_{best(s+1)}^i = \begin{cases} P_{best(s+1)}^i & \text{if } f(P_{best(s+1)}^i) < f(G_{best(s)}^i) \\ G_{best(s)}^i & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{19}$$

- d) Increment s , if $s > N_s$ go to step (x) else go to step (a)

(xi) Increment j , if $j > N_c$ go to step (7) else go to step (v)

7. Perform population reproduction. The BFOA reproduction stage is also modified using GA and DE variants. Roulette wheel selection is used to get the parents from the current population. The probability of a bacterium to be chosen/selected as a parent is given by (20).

$$p_{(\theta^i)} = \frac{f(\theta_{best(N_c,k,l)}^i)}{\sum_{i=1}^N f(\theta_{best(N_c,k,l)}^i)}, \quad i \in N \tag{20}$$

Where, $f(\theta_{best(N_c,k,l)}^i)$ is the fitness of i^{th} individual in the population.

Based on arithmetic crossover, the new population is obtained from the parents as given in (21) and (22).

$$\theta_{N_c,k+1,l}^{i(new_1)} = \lambda \theta_{best(N_c,k,l)}^{i(old_1)} + (1 - \lambda) \theta_{best(N_c,k,l)}^{i(old_2)} \tag{21}$$

$$\theta_{N_c,k+1,l}^{i(new_2)} = \lambda \theta_{best(N_c,k,l)}^{i(old_2)} + (1 - \lambda) \theta_{best(N_c,k,l)}^{i(old_1)} \tag{22}$$

Where, λ is a random integer between 0 & 1.

- 8. Increment k , if $k > K$ go to step (11) else go to step (6)
- 9. Perform Elimination/Dispersal stage: Half of the population (those with the worst fitness) are replaced with randomly assigned new positions in the solution space (similar to the population initialization in step 2) and the other bacteria with the better fitness values are maintained.
- 10. Increment l , if $l > L$ go to step (11) else go to step (5).
- 11. Output the positions and the fitness of all bacteria in the population. The bacteria with the latest G_{best} becomes the optimal solution for the optimization problem.

TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed meta-heuristic based adaptive hybrid algorithm was tested on various standard benchmark functions and constrained engineering test problems. The developed algorithm and the test problems were programmed on MATLAB 2014 software. The obtained results were compared with those obtained by other researchers using available optimization techniques. The following parameters for the developed algorithm were used in the test analysis:

Table -2 ADEBFOA Parameter Setting

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Population size	N	100
Chemotactic steps	N_c	25
Swim length	N_s	4
Reproduction steps	K	4
Elimination/Dispersal steps	L	2
Step-size limits	C_{min}, C_{max}	0.03, 0.07
Mutation probability	P_{mut}	0.025

Standard Benchmark Functions

These functions are often used by researchers to examine the performance of developed optimization algorithms/ techniques. In this analysis both high dimensional (F1-F10) and low dimensional (F11-F20) test functions were employed. Emphasizes was on the high dimensional continuous functions whose dimensionality makes them difficult to solve [13]. Detailed information on the standard benchmark functions applied here can be obtained in [13 & 14] where the dimensionality and modality (unimodal or multimodal) of individual functions are given. Metaheuristic based optimization techniques are usually stochastic in nature and thus their performance cannot be judged in a single run [13], as a result an average of 50 runs was used for the comparisons in this paper. The normalization procedure given in [15] is used to facilitate authentic comparison between results obtained from different algorithms. The procedure employs equation (23):

$$f_{i,norm} = \left\{ 1 - \frac{(f_i - f_{min})}{(f_{max} - f_{min})} \right\} \quad (23)$$

Where $f_{i,norm}$ is the normalized value, f_i is the fitness value, f_{min} and f_{max} are the minimum and maximum fitness values of solution i . Table-3 gives the comparison between results of the developed metaheuristic-based adaptive hybrid technique and those of other metaheuristic algorithms.

Table -3 Statistical Result Comparison for Benchmark Functions

Benchmark Function	Result Feature	PSO [16]	BBO [16]	DE [16]	FFA [16]	ADEBFOA [This Method]
F1 (Ackley)	Best	0.8561	0.9125	0.1279	0.9878	0.99889
	Mean	0.7351	0.8924	0.0000	0.9733	0.98053
	Std dev.	0.7742	0.2514	0.9875	0.7126	0.54172
F2 (Griewank)	Best	0.8016	0.9235	0.0001	0.9616	0.96640
	Mean	0.6842	0.9014	0.0000	0.9324	0.91320
	Std dev.	0.5585	0.5197	0.1013	0.9102	0.62140
F3 (Rosenbrock)	Best	0.9954	0.9672	0.2541	0.9871	1.00000
	Mean	0.9512	0.9201	0.2435	0.9239	0.99255
	Std dev.	0.7649	0.5148	0.3512	0.6284	0.26356
F4 (Schwefel 2.26)	Best	0.9012	0.8921	0.6214	0.8743	0.93511
	Mean	0.8903	0.8315	0.4240	0.8272	0.87468
	Std dev.	0.5541	0.5148	0.8476	0.7513	0.59305
F5 (Schwefel 2.22)	Best	0.7549	0.7894	0.6259	0.9006	0.98624
	Mean	0.7158	0.7515	0.3682	0.8851	0.90264
	Std dev.	0.5541	0.8457	0.9845	0.6022	0.63540
F6 (Schwefel 2.21)	Best	0.8128	0.9459	0.7547	1.0000	0.98973
	Mean	0.7420	0.9025	0.6789	1.0000	0.96246
	Std dev.	0.3518	0.4875	0.8452	0.9638	0.47513
F7 (Schwefel 1.2)	Best	0.6742	0.9845	0.0000	0.9920	0.99072
	Mean	0.6315	0.9125	0.0000	0.9770	0.95284
	Std dev.	0.6842	0.5148	0.0000	0.7516	0.70122
F8 (Sphere)	Best	0.7155	0.8965	0.6025	1.0000	1.00000
	Mean	0.6879	0.8823	0.5942	0.9703	0.98564
	Std dev.	0.6658	0.5129	0.9551	0.7125	0.81546
F9 (Rastrigin)	Best	0.9727	0.9621	0.6745	0.9615	0.97762
	Mean	0.9523	0.9222	0.6424	0.9324	0.94285
	Std dev.	0.5135	0.6541	0.8845	0.9103	0.87583
F10 (Quatric)	Best	0.9021	0.9925	0.8992	0.9872	0.99925
	Mean	0.8999	0.9401	0.8422	0.9238	0.92856
	Std dev.	0.3513	0.6846	0.6584	0.6284	0.78961

From the results tabulated in Table II above, the developed metaheuristic-based adaptive hybrid algorithm (ADEBFOA) produced better results in eight (out of the ten standard benchmark functions) tests when compared to the other metaheuristic methods. Only in F6 (Schwefel 2.21) and F7 (Schwefel 1.2) functions where the developed algorithm was outperformed by the FireFly Algorithm (FFA). The results obtained in these two functions are however very close to those of FFA. The testing of the algorithm performance having shown promising results from the high dimensional standard benchmark functions was extended to selected representative constrained engineering optimization problems.

Constrained Engineering Test Problems

Two constrained engineering problems have been used frequently in open literature to test effectiveness of developed optimization algorithms. These two problems are the pressure vessel design and spring design.

Pressure Vessel Design Optimization

Equation (24) gives the cost function of the pressure vessel design optimization problem as given in [17].

$$Cost(x) = 0.6224x_1x_3x_4 + 1.7781x_2x_3^3 + 3.1661x_1^2x_4 + 19.84x_1^2x_3 \tag{24}$$

The equation is minimized subject to constraints (25-28):

$$f_1(x) = (-x_1 + 0.0193x_3) \leq 0 \tag{25}$$

$$f_2(x) = (-x_2 + 0.00954x_3) \leq 0 \tag{26}$$

$$f_3(x) = \{-(\pi x_3^2 x_4^2) - (\frac{4}{3}\pi x_3) + 1296000\} \leq 0 \tag{27}$$

$$f_4(x) = (x_4 - 240) \leq 0 \tag{28}$$

The thickness of the cylinder and head, x_1 and x_2 respectively are discrete variables and can only take integer multiples of 0.0625 inches while the diameter and length of the vessel, x_3 and x_4 are continuous variables.

The bounds for x_1 and x_2 are given by $x_1 \geq 1 \times 0.0625$, $x_2 \leq 99 \times 0.0625$ respectively.

The problem is solved in two regions where:

Region I: $x_4 \leq 200$

Region II: $10 \leq x_3 \leq 200$ and $10 \leq x_4 \leq 240$

Tables-4&5 give the statistical result comparison between the developed algorithm and other metaheuristic-based algorithms in regions I & II respectively.

Table -4 Result Comparison for Pressure Vessel Design Optimization Problem - Region I

Parameter	Optimization Algorithm				
	PSO [18]	GA [19]	ACO [20]	ES [21]	ADEBFOA [This Method]
Cost(x)	6059.721	6059.946	6059.726	6059.746	6059.719
f1(x)	-8.8E-07	-2.02E-05	-1.79E-06	-6.9E-06	1.05E-06
f2(x)	-0.03588	-0.03589	-0.03588	-0.03588	-0.03588
f3(x)	-521.857	-546.549	-521.682	-518.735	-524.303
f4(x)	-63.363	-63.346	-63.362	-63.359	-63.364
x1	0.8125	0.8125	0.8125	0.8125	0.8125
x2	0.4375	0.4375	0.4375	0.4375	0.4375
x3	42.0984	42.0974	42.0984	42.0981	42.0985
x4	176.6372	176.6541	176.6378	176.641	176.6364
Best	6059.721	6059.946	6059.726	6059.746	6059.719
Mean	6440.379	6177.253	6081.781	6850.005	6082.570
Std Dev.	448.471	130.930	67.242	426.000	45.702

Table -5 Result Comparison for Pressure Vessel Design Optimization Problem - Region II

Parameter	Optimization Algorithm				
	PSO [22]	FFA [23]	HS [24]	EA [25]	ADEBFOA [This Method]
Cost(x)	5875.166	5850.383	5852.639	5850.383	5849.728
f1(x)	-0.00340	-7E-08	-0.00031	-7E-08	-0.00019
f2(x)	-0.00595	-0.00427	-0.00443	-0.00427	-0.00437
f3(x)	-506.790	-521.510	-523.682	-521.463	-41.152
f4(x)	-15.910	-18.635	-18.388	-18.635	-18.586
x1	0.7500	0.7500	0.7500	0.7500	0.7500
x2	0.3750	0.3750	0.3750	0.3750	0.3750
x3	38.6840	38.8601	38.8441	38.8601	38.8504
x4	224.09	221.3655	221.6125	221.3655	221.4136
Best	5875.166	5850.383	5852.639	5850.383	5849.728
Mean	6032.740	5937.338	6083.339	5925.650	5871.985
Std Dev.	315.149	164.547	140.450	150.534	44.514

Tension/Compression Spring Design Optimization Problem

The cost function for the spring design optimization problem is given by equation (29) while equations (30-33) give the associated constraints [17].

$$Cost(x) = (x_3 + 2)x_2x_1^2 \tag{29}$$

$$f_1(x) = \{1 - (\frac{x_3^2x_3}{7178x_1^4})\} \leq 0 \tag{30}$$

$$f_2(x) = \left\{ \left(\frac{4x_2^2 - x_1x_2}{12566(x_2x_3^3) - x_1^4} \right) + \left(\frac{1}{5108x_1^2} \right) - 1 \right\} \leq 0 \quad (31)$$

$$f_3(x) = \left\{ 1 - \left(\frac{140.45x_1}{x_2^2x_3} \right) \right\} \leq 0 \quad (32)$$

$$f_4(x) = \left\{ \frac{(x_1+x_2)}{1.5} - 1 \right\} \leq 0 \quad (33)$$

The simple bounds for the spring design problem are given by:

$$0.05 \leq x_1 \leq 2.0, 0.25 \leq x_2 \leq 1.3 \text{ and } 2.0 \leq x_3 \leq 15.0$$

The comparison between the obtained best solution for the developed ADEBFOA algorithm and those obtained by various researchers using other metaheuristic-based algorithms is given in Table-6.

Table-6 Result Comparison for Tension/Compression Spring Design Optimization Problem

Parameter	Optimization Algorithm					
	GA [26]	PSO [27]	ES [28]	DE [29]	FFA [30]	ADEBFOA [This Method]
Cost(x)	0.012705	0.012675	0.012698	0.012748	0.012667	0.012666
f1(x)	-9.034065	-9.008948	-9.018026	-9.000686	-9.001002	-8.990954
f2(x)	-0.135661	-0.134066	-0.135133	-0.122109	-0.134734	-0.134904
f3(x)	-4.026318	-4.051307	-4.039301	-4.149707	-4.050127	-4.054598
f4(x)	-0.731239	-0.727085	-0.728665	-0.689903	-0.728850	-0.728270
x1	0.051480	0.051728	0.051643	0.053862	0.051623	0.051665
x2	0.351661	0.357644	0.355360	0.411284	0.355102	0.355930
x3	11.632201	11.244543	11.397926	8.684380	11.385602	11.331890
Best Solution	0.012705	0.012675	0.012698	0.012748	0.012667	0.012666

The obtained results for the constrained engineering optimization problems studied were very comparable to those obtained from other metaheuristic-based algorithms. The developed Adaptive Differential Evolution/Bacterial Foraging Optimization hybrid algorithm (ADEBFOA) produced better results in both optimization regions (I & II) for the pressure vessel design problem. In region I, the obtained result of 6059.719 was quite close to the true global optimum of 6059.714335048436 obtained using both Mathematical analysis and Lagrange multiplier methods [31]. The developed adaptive hybrid algorithm outperformed the results of the other five metaheuristic techniques as given in Table 4. The results from the developed algorithm for the tension/compression spring design optimization problem were also superior to those from the other five optimization techniques in comparison. However, the obtained result of 0.012666 was very close to that obtained by Yuksel C. & Hakan K. using Firefly Algorithm, that is 0.012667 as given in [30].

CONCLUSION

This paper presented a new methodology for solving constrained optimization problems. The paper gives a step by step analysis for developing an adaptive hybrid algorithm in which Differential Evolution (DE) & Bacterial Foraging Optimization Algorithm (BFOA) are hybridized and adapted using both Genetic and Swarm Intelligence operators. The developed ADEBFOA algorithm was tested using the Standard Benchmark Functions and produced promising results. The algorithm performed better than other metaheuristic methods in eight of the ten high dimensional functions (F1-F10) used. Having produced promising results on the Standard Benchmark Functions the developed algorithm was tested on constrained engineering optimization problems. The algorithm outperformed other metaheuristic optimization methods in the two constrained engineering problems solved (Pressure vessel design and tension/compression spring design problem). In both test cases, the developed algorithm was able to obtain better feasible solutions in majority of the test runs performed per problem. The results obtained show that the developed adaptive Differential Evolution/Bacterial Foraging Optimization hybrid algorithm (ADEBFOA) performs better in solving most complex constrained optimization problems. The future work of this research study is to use the developed algorithm in solving the highly dimensional, quite complex and non-linear power system expansion optimization problem.

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